

KJ Somaiya College of Arts and Commerce

MAHATMA GANDHI'S LETTERS ON BRAHMACHARYA SEXUALITY
AND LOVE

A Book Review

Suyashdeep Sason

Gandhism – Theory and Practice

Dr. Madhumita Bandyopadhyay

October 15, 2023

Gandhi – A man who has never been ordinary practically his entire life. And the list of reasons that made him the same, is almost an inexhaustive list, and continues to grow even 75 years after his death. Because as we dig deeper, we find newer and even more astonishing facts about him, his mind, and his actions. Gandhi was an imperfect Brahmachari, as he claimed the same. His views on Sexuality need a better word than mere ‘controversial’. His understanding of Love is still far ahead of our time to make sense of. This paper reviews and critically analyses Girja Kumar’s book – Mahatma Gandhi’s Letters on Brahmacharya Sexuality and Love. The paper becomes an essential guide to all the readers aspiring to read the book, and at the same time, it also coexists as a topic of discussion on the contents of it, post the read. It decodes and critically analyses Gandhi’s letters and gives a meaningful insight about the nature of his conversations with some important people in his life. It also discusses the observations of his core nature in general, and reviews the author’s take on him. His letters on Brahmarcharya, Sexuality and Love take us through a never-seen-before journey in which we see an even more ‘Gandhian’ version of Gandhi.

The inspiration for choosing this book to review was taken by a blog written by Rita Banerji in 2018.¹ Banerji’s blog remains the only work that’s connected to the book, in which she criticizes Gandhi for sexually abusing the girls in his ashram. It was a very specific issue that she focused upon in her blog that was just five percent of the whole book. She used the book to refer a few letters from.

Other than that, there are articles that discuss his views on sexuality, celibacy, *brahmacharya*, etc., individually but there are none that review the book. Which is how this book review becomes the first of its kind. The other articles on these topics are only the author’s reviews and analysis on Gandhi, his philosophies and experiments, but none contain the first-hand information, i.e., the actual letters, the way this book has.

The book ‘Mahatma Gandhi’s Letters on Brahmacharya Sexuality and Love’ in its totality has been used as a primary source to write this paper. Published in 2011, the book has a companion volume released in 2006 – Mahatma Gandhi and his Women Associates that the author advises to read if the reader wants to know the detailed background of the events mentioned in it.

The book reads out like a confessional and is divided into sections (six), with each section comprising their respective chapters under them. The first section is entirely dedicated to his wife Kasturba, to which special attention is given in the initial part of the paper. The sections that follow it are – his *Brahmacharya* in Theory and Practice, Married *Brahmacharya*, Noakhali Mahayajna, Foreign Associates, and Platonic Love. The book also mentions an Appendix on Gandhi's relationship with his 'soulmate' Hermann Kallenbach.

As aforementioned, the first part of the paper talks about his relationship with his wife Kasturba and him as a husband, through the letters he wrote to her. It is followed by the review of his *Brahmacharya* experiments and the letters he exchanged with his people conversing the same. It discusses topics like 'Physical Touch', 'Vital Energy', and 'Sleeping Together' in the form of chapters.

While reviewing the book, I have elaborated on some specific sections from these chapters to assist me in my analysis, such as the infamous interview of Gandhi with the well-known feminist Mrs. Margaret Sanger, or the letter that R.P. Parshuram wrote to Gandhi before quitting his job as his secretary.

The paper then individually reviews the book, the author, his writing style, and gives an overall summary on his work. Post that, I have reviewed my learnings about Gandhi as to how I have felt overall about him, after reading the book, and what changed perspective I have about him with this first-hand newfound knowledge about him.

Gandhi's letters to Kasturba

One gets to know a lot about the Gandhi's relationship with his wife Kasturba through the letters he wrote to her. Although we don't get to see both sides of the communication, we still get a very good idea on how Gandhi was as a husband.

Now it would be injustice if I said Gandhi was not a difficult husband to live with. We see this in many examples through his own communications to her, in his letters. And his infamous stubbornness was on point when it came to his married life too. For instance, in 1908 when Kasturba had seriously fallen ill and Gandhi was away, he wrote to her to check on her well-being.² But he would not even go to visit her by compromising his principles and work. He was that stubborn on his principles of Satyagraha. For him, Satyagraha came even before his 'dying wife'. On one side, he talks so lovingly about feeling and caring for her, but on the

other side, he won't really visit her just to avoid the fine that he had to pay and break his Satyagraha.³

And then he goes on to say that even if she dies, the separation would not be wrong – *“If, however, my ill luck so has it that you pass away, I should only say that there would be nothing wrong in your doing so in your separation from me while I am still alive. I love you so dearly that even if you are dead, you will be alive to me”*.⁴

It's hard to guess if these statements that usually sound like dialogues were really heartfelt or whether they came from a place of emotionlessness (more examples ahead to support this) and made his romance seem pretentious. In fact, he says that even her death would be a sacrifice to the cause of Satyagraha! – *“If you die, even that death of yours will be a sacrifice to the cause of Satyagraha”*

It's a bit insane to believe in something in this way. Gandhi was obsessed with Satyagraha. The above quote made very little sense. He lived in his own world by self-claiming the reality to be what it 'should be' according to him. But it isn't really. For example, when death really comes, Kasturba or anyone might not even really care a dime about devoting their life for a mere 'cause' no matter how big or small it is; and here is Gandhi, who, is not even claiming his own but someone else's death as a sacrifice to his own cause. It just shows how much he lived in his own world, in his head, being actually disconnected from reality. He goes on to justify this crazy obsession with Satyagraha as being 'religious' and not merely 'political.'⁵

A few letters ahead we again witness an example of his bizarre philosophy. It was 1914 and Gandhi wrote to Maganlal Gandhi discussing Kasturba's critical health stage. He suggests some remedies to help her, like reciting the *Ramayana* to her, or singing prayer songs. But here he mentions how he's doing the remedies not with the priority to make her live, but to keep her 'pure'.⁶ In the next line he says he's prepared everything for her death too. This does show his strength but it again somewhere shows his emotionlessness in a way, as normal people with emotions are far from feeling this way. So he and his romantic emotions and philosophies when it came to his wife were definitely unique and unusual for sure.

In the later years, by 1914, there was a point in which his relation really deteriorated with Kasturba. He was done with her. In his letter to Herman Kallenbach, he gives the example of both devil and divine being in her equally.⁷ He is so fed up with her that he goes on to mention how he made her leave all the good food so that she dies; he wishes her death and calls

himself a hooded snake – “*I had made her leave all the good food in order to kill her, I was tired of her, I wished her to die, I was a hooded snake*” He also goes on to call her the most venomous woman he’s ever met.

In the same letter, he continues, “*but my love has not been sufficiently intense and selfless to make her ‘change her nature’*” – We see how he was someone who, despite not even willing to change his smallest of principles, or will, for anybody (even for his own dying wife as aforementioned), would expect his wife to ‘change her nature’ (something that actually can’t be). So when it came to the concept of ‘change’, we can definitely agree on Gandhi having some hypocritical traits. However, he does praise her and gives her credit too, within the same letter, which again shows how ‘practically emotional’ he was, becoming quite oxymoronic.

One example of how his views related to woman were very absurd and unusual is seen in the same letter when he mentions that “*you cannot attach yourself to a particular woman and yet live for humanity*” It only means how big of a deal it was for him to be attached to a woman, or how devoted he was, if into someone, or how demanding the role he had to play for the woman became, if it existed. The idea of being with someone was so ‘grand’ for him in a way that one couldn’t live for humanity if you’re attached to a particular person, something which as per popular and personal belief, is untrue.

A review on Gandhi’s *Brahmacharya*

Brahmacharya, according to Gandhi, was the “*complete control in thought, speech and action of all senses, at all places and at all times*”.⁸ It was the search for the ‘brahman’ within.

According to Gandhi, sex was in reality located in mind than in the groin.⁹ There’s no doubt that his obsession with *Brahmacharya* went to some insane limits. Sometimes he did go on too far and disrespectful when he commented that “*cutting off one’s organs could be a sacred duty*”¹⁰ for those people who were passionate in nature.¹¹ The irony of this is seen in the fact that Gandhi himself was subject to ‘involuntary discharges’ in his sleep during his late sixties, and the fact that he couldn’t control this troubled him more.¹²

Gandhiji’s stance of using sex only for procreation was also extremely unfair and insulting, on humanity and the basic human expression of making love. His advice to young couples to have sex once in two years just for procreation purposes and the fact that he used the term ‘animal passion’ for the basic sexual desire in human beings is just downright insulting

and unacceptable. It's very astonishing to know, or rather it makes sense now (that why he thinks the way he thinks), that Gandhi didn't even believe the science or the scientific facts behind sexual act, as he believed there are no mental, spiritual or physical benefits that are derived from the same.¹³

The author does a great job by covering and presenting the extracts of the infamous interview-debate that Gandhi had with the well-known feminist Margaret Sanger over *brahmacharya* and other topics like birth-control in which she successfully confronted him at many instances, and we got to know a lot about Gandhi's inner philosophy regarding those matters. In fact, so many of his statements are so baffling that he digs his own grave by uttering them, as they are so self-explanatory to disagree with.

Like in one instance, he says "*when both (partners) want to satisfy animal passion without having to suffer¹⁴ the consequences of their act, it is not love. It is lust.*" and continues "*When a husband says 'Let us not have children but have relations,' what is that but animal passion? If they do not want to have children they should simply refuse to unite*"¹⁵. It is so clear that he does not believe at all in sex love. Which is why right after that statement when Mrs. Sanger asks him whether this means that he believes that all sex union except for the purpose of having children is lust, he just simply says 'Yes'.¹⁶ Out of many things, one thing's very clear that he had a very twisted mindset regarding love. His rigid beliefs on sex and love as seen in the book sound very ignorant and yet filled with pride. It seems like his conscience on these issues (love, sex) came more from a place of emotion rather than logic or rationality.

He saw the concepts of love and lust in a very black and white manner. If one existed, the other couldn't. Which is never how it is, or has been. 'Love' is many things, and the physical attraction that arises due to it (the one that he calls 'lust') is just one of the beautiful expressions of it. Sex is just one of the expressions of love. But through the letters we see Gandhi constructed a very thick wall between them, claiming both to be two very different things. In the same interview, Mrs. Sanger very beautifully, using good vocabulary, goes on to explain to him the difference between love and lust, and the two different types of passion, and how they shouldn't be confused with,¹⁷ but he continues to tangle the thread more than untangling it.

"I know from my own experience that, as long as I looked upon my wife carnally, we had no real understanding".¹⁸ Again, a statement that is shockingly untrue. Basically, he had this belief that there cannot be love if there is sex/carnal relation between two people. For him, love only exists without the urge for sex. Now I agree, that can certainly be one type of love,

but by no means is that the only kind. He never understood that true love can exist *with* having a fair amount of physical intimacy, in fact it is a very necessary form of expression in love, in a relationship, according to science. Only exceptional & unusual cases like him tend to be mistaken that the absence of a sexual urge is the only definition of true love. It is mistaken to be ‘pure’ or ‘sacred’. Like he says that “*lust is clothed in the dress of love*”,¹⁹ the actual reality is that his philosophy of abstaining from sexual intimacy to share the so-called ‘true love’ with someone is in fact clothed in the dress of ‘purity’ or ‘sacredness’ whereas it is far from being that.

Parshuram’s Indictment

This was my favorite part of the book, a part of which I had read in Rita Banerji’s blog²⁰ which is what actually drew me to read this book. As a general student, my knowledge about history was limited to what I learnt in school, along with the general history we get to read here and there over the years. But a few years back, I came across a blog written by Rita Banerji and it just took me by shock, as I was never aware of the history about Gandhi apart from what I had read in school textbooks. The curiosity to know more always stayed within, and through this paper I ultimately got a chance to bring back that thought and study the entire narrative thoroughly in order to do justice before making any judgements about him.

R.P. Parshuram was the private secretary and typist of Gandhi for a brief period. He resigned from his job after he was disturbed with certain actions of Gandhi with females in the *ashram* especially his sexual experiments. Before he quit, he wrote a 16-page letter to him. He called it his letter of ‘indictment’. The book obviously contains ‘extracts’ of the letter which only covers the main issues with which Parshuram had problems with. He starts by mentioning how painful it is for him to do this (writing the letter) but he was left with no choice.

He says, “*When I first came to the ashram I came with high respect for the ashram and its inmates and its way of life. All that was knocked off in 24 hours. But the respect for you increased.*”. He spoke about the good things that Gandhi had done for the nation, and that he was a man who is born once in 5 to 600 years. He spoke about how Gandhi had done so much for our freedom and independence, shook the Hindu’s conception of untouchability, and much more. Finally, he starts by headlining his first complaint with Gandhi – He wanted Dr. Sushilabehn (Gandhi’s doctor) to leave him. He had a bad instinct about her and said that he

will disgrace him one day. She didn't imbibe any of Gandhi's principles, had no conception of Swadeshi, could not live a life of discomfort, did not know how to behave, and was rude to people. He said Gandhi was like wax in her hands. He asked him these rhetorical questions –

“How many are the days when she has not wept? She is a doctor and yet she is always a patient, always is ill. Who has heard of a doctor who cries out at night. Can she find no cure for it? She is supposed to be your doctor... yet she is the first criminal in upsetting your health as well as mental peace.”

According to him, she was only with him because she got the opportunity to shine in reflected glory. He even told him to ask this to anybody including Patel, his own sons Manilal and Devdas, or ask the whole world for that matter, and they would agree that she should leave him. He commented this on Gandhi's role in his home – *“To me, you appear to be a complete flop in household affairs. You commit Himalayan blunders. But you refuse to see these things and when told, you get irritated.”*

His second complaint was that Pyarelal's (Gandhi's personal secretary) affair with Manu Gandhi should not be continued. He said he would leave if these demands are not met. However, the main complaints come after this where he objects some controversial actions of Gandhi-

“Your actions to which I object:

- 1. Your sleeping with any member of the opposite sex*
- 2. Being massaged by any member of the opposite sex*
- 3. Allowing yourself to be seen naked by any member of the opposite sex*
- 4. Allowing yourself to be seen naked by strangers and even by people who are of your party who are not so intimate.*
- 5. Placing your hands on the shoulders of girls when walking.*

These also I have reduced to five. The first 2 are more important than the others.”

He then went on to elaborate in detail on each action individually. These revelations by Parshuram become extremely significant in observing Gandhi's sexual experiments from a third-person's view for the first time in a proper established manner. His words sound extremely convincing, and it can be seen how emotionally he wrote it, the emotion is felt in the read. Once again, the author does a great job here by prioritizing the correct sections of his 16-

page letter to be included in the book, that help the reader to get a complete idea of how he took out his frustration on Gandhi and for which reasons.

In my most honest opinion, I did not like this side about Gandhi as I read this part. The blog by Rita Banerji as aforementioned also focused on this extract to talk about the sexual abuse done by Gandhi on the girls in his *ashram*. Reading this section made me dislike him for what he did. It felt it was unfair, unethical and immoral it was for Gandhi to conduct these experiments and activities with these girls without having their consent.

If that wasn't enough, what was even more shocking than this was Gandhi's response to it. Instead of being sorry or realizing his mistakes, Gandhi being Gandhi, doubled down on it and rather accepted Parshuram's departure if that's what the condition was, rather than justifying and cleaning his image and convince Parshuram to stay, especially after knowing how upset he was.

About the Book

The book is not completely a finished work, as the author mentions there is a companion volume to the same – *Brahmacharya, Gandhi and His Women Associates* and advises to read along with it in order to get a detailed background of the incidents. They are independent works but closely related to each other. Nonetheless, while actually reading one doesn't feel the need of having external sources to understand the things discussed, leaving a handful terms or incidents, but they could purely be due to my lack of knowledge about them.

Although the title of the book says it's about his 'letters', the book also contains other pieces of writings like his speeches, or his interview with Mrs. Sanger, etc. The structure of the book is nicely designed. The preface of the book acts the introduction and feels like reading a book in itself, due to its detailed summary on different aspects covered beautifully by the author. From Gandhi being a 'Ladies' Man', his 'Platonic Love', up to his bond with 'Charismatic Kallenbach', the short segments create a very intriguing environment for the reader to just turn pages and dive into the reading. In so many ways, it acts like a conclusion for many topics as it contains the summary of what is deduced after going through the letters of any particular topic.²¹

As each chapter begins, the book first mentions the author's summary of the upcoming letters in the topic before we read the actual letters. Now this becomes very helpful in every

case. The reader gets a good idea beforehand of what they're going to expect in the letters, it helps to give context to the letters, and many a times it also acts like the explanation of the letters in a simple manner as the actual letters are original talks which can be perceived wrongly by anybody if not read in the right context. The titles in the start of the letters are also named well and become very helpful in knowing what the letter is going to be about.

The book mentions 'extracts' of each letter that focus on the main parts which make it easier for the reader to get the crux of the issue and get insights without having to read the entire letter which may have included other irrelevant parts to the topic. However, at many instances it became very necessary to have a prior summary about them so as to understand the context and topic about which they are written on. Without the author's inputs, the book that would have just contained Gandhi's letters (without any context or historical background) would have been very complex to read, understand and make sense of, let alone analyze.

The book's back cover is also well written and gives the reader crucial information on what not to miss, and the same time, does not spoil anything for them. Almost all e-commerce websites have used the same content word by word in their description for the book.

When it comes to Gandhi's letters, they're very well compiled by the author and one doesn't feel short of content when it comes to reading the letters of a particular topic. In fact, it does feel like an overdose of letters sometimes and makes the reader feel like moving on to the next topic, after the interesting and controversial part of it has been read. The only downside is some of the letters often sound very repetitive, and get a bit boring to read for many topics. At many instances you feel like reading the author's summary of the letters rather than reading the actual letters as it demands a lot of conscious analyzation to even understand the simplest of talks that Gandhi is having with his people.

Another important thing to note is that the book mentions one-sided letters from Gandhi to his people, except a few responses by others in the 'Controversies' chapters. So, although we learn a lot about Gandhi through this, it doesn't help us fully understand his dynamics with those people whom he wrote to as we do not get to see their side of communication that was written back to Gandhi. At many instances, there is no background context to understand what are the characters talking about, so it becomes difficult to fully understand the depth of the topic they're talking about, or what the author wants the reader to feel. Complex issues are discussed without context. Many topics are just bouncers due to the same reason. A simple example is discussed in the second paragraph of this paper regarding the fine that Gandhi did

not want to pay to meet Kasturba,²² that's discussed above in Kasturba's segment. Here, the reader does not understand the background of the same, as to what exactly was the fine about, or how much was the fine amount, etc.

Although the title of the book itself talks about letters, the book does not contain just the latter. Along with letters, there are other important pieces of short information too that are mentioned in the book, in the Controversies (I and II) section. These are short topics which didn't need or couldn't fit in a chapter of their own, and hence included in this section and the author gives them suitable titles. In fact, these topics help us understand and give us a slight insight about what others felt about Gandhi.

One of the best parts about the entire book comes in this very section, and it is the segment of Parshuram ('Parshuram's Indictment') in which he beautifully criticizes Gandhi for a lot of his sexual practices and other complaints regarding the people around him. He says the things I would have said if I were in his place. He speaks for the people. It feels like he becomes our advocate even before we read ahead to know the truth. Reading his part gave a sense of satisfaction.

About the Author

The author Girja Kumar has beautifully mentioned the summary of each topic before presenting the letters about them. By using simple vocabulary, understanding his language was never a task. He gives us a good insight and helps us to really understand the gist of what Gandhi is trying to speak in those letters, as the language of the letters was not always easy to decipher. In these summaries, the author has included the important points in a very fair manner. He explained everything very clearly, factually and with full honesty without trying to defame him or make him a God.

As aforementioned, he did criticize and praised him wherever needed, but at no point does the reader feel like the author came from a biased place and neither did any of it reflect in his tone or writing style either. I connected with them so well that it felt like it was almost the same way I would have summarized if I was reviewing Gandhi's letters. He has done justice to them.

One of the best parts about Kumar's writing style is how open and unbiased he remained while speaking truth about many sensitive and controversial issues of Gandhi's life. It felt like a hesitation-free writing.

The author gives Gandhi credit wherever deserved, and equally criticizes him wherever he had to be. We see a beautiful example of this in the book where he gives him credit for placing *Brahmacharya* in the frontline confronting human existence, but he blames him for not placing all his cards on the table, i.e., not sharing his tactics and strategies to achieve *nirvana* while practicing *brahmacharya* and keeping his associates always in the dark about his intentions.²³

About Gandhi

Through the course of the book, one thing I realized, is that Gandhi was definitely way ahead of his time, especially when it comes to the philosophies he discussed in this book – whether his *brahmacharya*, or his sexual experiments, be it anything. In fact, even if he was born today, his lifestyle and philosophy would have been still ahead of what an average educated man thinks and believes. So it's really fascinating to realize that a man with a mind like that, existed a century ago.

Another thing that I felt after reading his letters was how much he lay down his own extremely personal self-introspections out there for the world to know, through his letters. With zero filters, things that one would not even want to discuss with their own conscience, he would discuss it with his associates. He completely postmortem-ed his mind out there for everyone to know and his conscience co-existed with theirs too, allowing them to take part in his introspections.

Many a times his letters felt like I was reading the transcript of a counselling session between a patient and his counsellor. And, a lot of the times I felt he even stretched and magnified many issues too, which are not worthy of being given that much importance. For instance, he experienced a nocturnal emission in a dream of his on 14th April, 1938.²⁴ Now, an average person forgets fifty percent of his dream in the first five minutes and ninety percent by the ten-minute mark.²⁵ But not for Gandhi. The man just simply did not even let his dream be a dream. He discussed, analysed, introspected, guilt-tripped on that dream with so many people by mentioning about it in countless letters to his associates like Mirabehn, Amrit Kaur, Pyarelal,

all his ashram associates, and maybe many others who aren't mentioned in the book.²⁶ As a reader I felt frustrated at a point to see how a dream is being taken so seriously and stretched unnecessarily. He just had to simply let go which he didn't.

And the way he introspected about it at a particular point in one of his letters to the Ashram inmates,²⁷ the number of introspective questions he writes for himself while analysing that one single dream is just astonishing –

“But a doubt arose after my experience of the 7th April.²⁸ Why have I not become free from passion in spite of my constant efforts towards Brahmacharya? Why have my thoughts and my mind not become purer and purer? I can say that I have not felt myself free from carnal desire in India as much as I did in South Africa. Could the contact with women have obstructed my path in some subtle way? Who can answer that question? The only solution is that unless God Himself answers it, I should try to shun all physical touch and understand my own mind and conquer it.”

This is a perfect example of the issues discussed above. He's putting his deepest introspections out there, he's experiencing extreme overthinking over a wet dream, stretching it to the limit, without considering whether his inmates even want to know about such personal information that can make anybody very uncomfortable.

It made me realize he considers himself and these personal thoughts of his too important.²⁹ As if it's the only thing that matters, and that the world was out of relevant issues. Reading that anybody would feel (respectfully) that they couldn't care less, and there are tons of other valid things to share and talk about, these being extremely irrelevant and too personal of them.

When it comes to sexuality, in contrary to what Gandhi has claimed about himself, I feel Gandhi was actually a very sexual person with a very high sex-drive probably, which is why he made the talk around it so big. Sex actually took a very big place in his life, otherwise he wouldn't have made so much noise around it. People who really do not believe or do not like something, they simply don't talk about it so much. But his strong opinions, discussions, claims, etc. about sex just make it even simpler to deduce that he was in fact very much influenced and affected by sexuality, irrespective of which direction it was in.

For a change of topic, I realized after reading his direct words for the first time through this book – he surely had great command over the language. He used to write his letters like an

author writing a book. And in fact, not just him, but all of those who have exchanged letters with him. One can notice how different the English language used to be back then, oral and written. It was spoken a bit differently, something you don't get to see anymore.

Through this book we get to see so many of Gandhi's philosophies in life. Controversial, deep, futuristic, absurd, insane – these are some of the common adjective options one would use in order to describe them.

However, one of the best things about reading this book was that unlike other books, it gave us the rawest, deepest, and purest version of Gandhi as reading his own words felt very different from what we have read about him in third person in general, all our lives, barring his obvious quotes and statements in history that we have studied. It gives us a very fresh perspective in knowing Gandhi as to what kind of a person he was, from the core.

Conclusion

The journey through the book was many things but one. It was revealing, educating, eye opening, and most importantly, a lot of knowing. I got to know about Gandhi as a person and the kind of life they lived back then.

As for Gandhi's letters, they were definitely unusual, deeply philosophical, sometimes shocking, and at times boring too. I would be lying if I said I wasn't expecting anything normal but the level of what I experienced was something that I really didn't expect. However, 'love and affection' was the common tone that I found in literally all his letters.

If you take out Gandhi's identity from the picture and just read the letters purely for their content, one would definitely feel that the person who has penned them is definitely someone who stands out of the crowd. Someone who isn't a 'part of the matrix.' One who doesn't fit in the general society, by his thoughts, philosophies and beliefs.

The book really stands out from the usual books on Gandhi and the reason is unlike a biography or an autobiography, which can also be a consciously edited version of the one's actual personality, this book directly lets us read Gandhi's mind, unfiltered. I do not think there was a better way to understand his views, opinions, beliefs on *Brahmacharya*, Sexuality and Love by directly getting first-hand information from Gandhi himself, through his own words. Knowing Gandhi couldn't get more personal than this.

No matter how the events of his life would have turned up, he was definitely a person who was meant to come in public eye due to all these controversial and unconventional traits and nature that he was made up of. His popularity could have gone either way; either he would've been an outcast in the society or either he would go on to become the 'Mahatma' of the people. And we know which direction it went in. Otherwise, 78 years after his death, we wouldn't still be studying and talking about him.

ENDNOTES

¹ "On Gandhi's Sexual Abuse of Girls in His Ashram." *REVOLUTIONS IN MY SPACE: A BLOG BY RITA BANERJI*, 25 Feb. 2018, ritabanerjisblog.wordpress.com/2018/02/22/on-gandhis-sexual-abuse-of-girls-in-his-ashram.

² Girja Kumar, *Mahatma Gandhi's Letters on Brahmacharya Sexuality and Love*, Vitasta Publishing, 2011, p. 6

³ A later reference to this is done in the section 'About the book', 7th paragraph.

⁴ Kumar, *Op.cit.*

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ *Ibid.* p. 10

⁷ *Ibid.* p. 12

⁸ *Ibid.* p. 29

⁹ *Ibid.* pp. 25-26

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ Gandhi's letter to Raoji Patel, 7 March 1914, pp. 27-28

¹² Kumar, *Op.cit.* pp. 25-26, 30. Noteworthy that Gandhi used the word 'unclean' to describe these thoughts that he received in his sleep, which led to that activity.

¹³ *Ibid.* p. 27

¹⁴ He uses the word 'suffer' for the consequences of the sexual act which tells us how negatively he sees this process if it's not for having children. As if one has to 'suffer' the consequences (having a child) mandatorily after having sex.

¹⁵ Kumar, *Op.cit.*

¹⁶ *Ibid.* p. 49.

¹⁷ *Ibid.* pp. 49-50

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ Banerji, *op.cit.*

²¹ For instance, the ‘Public Acceptance’ section concludes Gandhi’s *brahmacharya* and sexual experiments by stating ‘Gandhi is also to be blamed for not placing all his cards on the table. In other words, he did not share both strategy and tactics to achieve the state of *nirvana* through practicing *brahmacharya* with others.’

²² *Ibid.* p. 6

²³ Page numbers not officially mentioned in Preface, however, it’s mentioned in the ‘Public Acceptance’ paragraph on page 4.

²⁴ Nothing new, it was normal for him to experience these, this is just the specific one that I used to explain the point.

²⁵ Obringer, Lee Ann, and Yves Jeffcoat. “How Dreams Work.” *HowStuffWorks*, Oct. 2021, science.howstuffworks.com/life/inside-the-mind/human-brain/dream4.htm#:~:text=It%20is%20said%20that%20five,our%20daily%20actions%20that%20quickly.

²⁶ *Op.cit.* pp. 69, 70, 71, 79, 96.

²⁷ Gandhi’s letter to Ashram Inmates, 2 June 1938. The second paragraph of page 97.

²⁸ Gandhi’s talking about the involuntary discharge he experienced in his sleep. There was another on 14th April.

²⁹ For the world to know, since he’s writing all of this to ‘people’, something that’s supposed to be a self-talk.

WORKS CITED

Betts, Jennifer. “MLA Paper Format: Simple Guidelines to Follow | Bibliography.com.” *Bibliography.com*, 30 Aug. 2020, www.bibliography.com/mla/mla-paper-format-simple-guidelines-to-follow.

“Creating an MLA Title Page | EasyBib.” *EasyBib Blog*, 21 June 2022, www.easybib.com/guides/citation-guides/mla-format/title-page-format-mla.

Kumar, Girja. *Mahatma Gandhi’s Letters on Brahmacharya Sexuality and Love*. Times Groups Books, 2011.

Mahatma Gandhi's Letters on Bhrahmacharya Sexuality and Love | Exotic India Art.
www.exoticindiaart.com/book/details/mahatma-gandhi-s-letters-on-bhrahmacharya-sexuality-and-love-nag926.

“On Gandhi’s Sexual Abuse of Girls in His Ashram.” *REVOLUTIONS IN MY SPACE: A BLOG BY RITA BANERJI*, 25 Feb. 2018, ritabanerjisblog.wordpress.com/2018/02/22/on-gandhis-sexual-abuse-of-girls-in-his-ashram.

Obringer, Lee Ann, and Yves Jeffcoat. “How Dreams Work.” *HowStuffWorks*, Oct. 2021, science.howstuffworks.com/life/inside-the-mind/human-brain/dream4.htm#:~:text=It%20is%20said%20that%20five,our%20daily%20actions%20that%20quickly.

Scribbr. “Scribbr - Your Path to Academic Success.” *Scribbr*, 21 Aug. 2023, www.scribbr.com.
Grammarly's Free Grammar Checker. www.grammarly.com/grammar-check.